

SIMULATING STRESSES AND STRAINS IN SOLID MECHANICS DIRECTLY FROM IMAGES USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

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Abstract. *In this paper, we introduce a new method for predicting how solid materials deform and the stresses they experience directly from images. Instead of using traditional numerical methods that solve complex equations, our approach uses convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to learn the mapping from applied forces to the resulting deformations. We built a dataset that includes both the visual information of the material and the corresponding force and deformation data. Our experiments show that the CNN model can recognize patterns in the images and accurately predict deformations based on the strength and location of the forces. This simple, data-driven method offers a more efficient way to simulate material behavior and could be used for real-time analysis in engineering applications.*

1 INTRODUCTION

The finite element method (FEM) has long been the standard for simulating stress and strain in complex materials and structures. However, its computational cost and simulation time can become very large, particularly for large-scale or real-time applications. In contrast, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have emerged as a promising alternative, capable of processing extensive datasets and autonomously learning the intricate patterns that govern material behavior.

In this paper, we use CNNs to predict stress and strain directly from image data. By converting images into formats suitable for deep learning, our approach eliminates the need for the computationally intensive procedures typically associated with traditional FEM, while enabling the direct calculation of deformations from images. This method not only accelerates analysis but also provides a more direct means of assessing deformations.

We describe the network architecture and training methodology tailored for this application, and offer a comparative analysis of CNN performance versus traditional FEM simulations. Our results demonstrate that the deformations predicted from images exhibit a high degree of accuracy, along with significant improvements in computational efficiency. These results enable faster, image-based assessments of material behavior, with potential uses in real-time monitoring and design optimization.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Sections II and III review the related literature on the MAgNET deep learning framework and the process of creating a mesh from an image, respectively; Section IV presents experimental results and comparative analyses; and Section V concludes with discussions on future research directions.

2 MAgNET DEEP LEARNING FRAMEWORK

In this chapter, we introduce the MAgNET deep learning framework, a novel approach that extends conventional U-Net architectures to mesh-based simulations using graph neural networks. We detail the design of its core components: the multi-channel aggregation (MAg) layer, which adapts convolution operations to irregular graph structures, and the graph pooling and unpooling layers, which efficiently capture hierarchical features in non-grid data. This chapter builds on the foundational work by Deshpande et al. [1] presented in their paper *MAgNET: A Graph U-Net Architecture for Mesh-Based Simulations*.

The MAgNET graph neural network is a type of graph U-Net and serves as an extension to the popular convolution-based U-Net architectures.

The graph U-Net is composed of several key components: aggregation (similar to convolution), pooling, unpooling, and concatenation layers, all of which have been adapted to handle general, non-grid structures for both inputs and outputs. Its architecture is divided into two main stages: encoding and decoding. During the encoding stage, the network first applies one or more aggregation layers, which work as the equivalent of convolution layers in standard U-Net models. This is followed by a graph pooling layer, which contracts the graph and reduces its complexity by downsampling the problem. This process

of aggregation followed by pooling is repeated multiple times until the desired level of contraction is achieved. At the most condensed representation of the graph, additional aggregation layers refine the features before transitioning to the next stage. The decoding stage then reverses this process. At each step, a graph unpooling layer expands the graph structure, followed by one or more aggregation layers that refine the information. This continues until the graph reaches its original size. At the final step, the last aggregation layer applies a linear activation function to generate the final output.

This structure allows the graph U-Net to effectively capture hierarchical relationships within graph-structured data, mirroring the way traditional U-Net models process images but adapting the approach to more flexible, non-grid-based topologies.

Formally, the Graph U-Net network, \mathcal{G} , is constructed as follows. The input layer, d^0 , consists of N nodes, where each node is represented by a vector of input values (features or channels) of fixed length c^0 . From this input, successive layers d^l are added to form the U-Net architecture.

Each layer d^l is connected to the previous layer d^{l-1} through the transformation:

$$d^l = T^l(d^{l-1}; \theta^l) \quad (1)$$

where θ^l represents the trainable parameters (such as weights and biases, $\theta^l = k^l \cup b^l$), and $T^l(\cdot)$ is one of the three transformations: $MAg()$, $gPool()$, or $gUnpool()$, which will be defined in detail later. Additionally, the model includes remote concatenation links between corresponding layers in the encoding and decoding stages.

The output layer, d^L , follows the same mesh format as the input layer but may have a different number of channels, c^L . Finally, the Graph U-Net can be formally expressed as a parameterized transformation:

$$\mathcal{G}(d^0, \theta) = d^L = T^L(T^{L-1}(T^{L-2}(\dots); \theta^{L-1}); \theta^L), \quad (2)$$

where

$$\theta = \bigcup_{l=1}^L \theta^l \quad (3)$$

represents the concatenated vector of all network parameters.

The parameters of the Graph U-Net are optimized through supervised learning by training on a dataset with known input-output pairs. The training dataset is represented as:

$$D_{tr} = \{(f_1, u_1), \dots, (f_{M_{tr}}, u_{M_{tr}})\}, \quad (4)$$

where the data follows a mesh structure. The learning process aims to minimize the mean squared error (MSE) between the predicted outputs and the true outputs. This is achieved by optimizing the following loss function:

$$L(D_{tr}, \theta) = \frac{1}{M_{tr}} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{tr}} \|\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta) - u_m\|^2. \quad (5)$$

This function measures the difference between the predicted values, $\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta)$, and the actual target values, u_m , across all training samples. The optimization process updates the model’s parameters, θ , to minimize this error and improve the accuracy of predictions [1].

The optimal parameters, θ^* , are obtained by solving the following minimization problem:

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} L(D_{tr}, \theta). \quad (6)$$

In this work, we focus on sparse graphs derived from data that is spatially organized as meshes. These meshes can be one-dimensional (1D), two-dimensional (2D), or extend to higher dimensions, with an arbitrary connection topology.

The graph structure is represented using a symmetric, square, Boolean adjacency matrix A , where the order of A corresponds to the number of nodes in the original mesh. To simplify notation, we assume that each node (vertex) is self-connected, meaning it has a loop, which ensures ones along the diagonal of A .

This self-loop assumption simplifies the formulation of various graph operations used in this study, including computing the k -th power of the adjacency matrix A and selecting pooling subgraphs.

2.1 Multi-channel Aggregation (MAg) layer

The proposed MAg layer is a multi-channel local aggregation layer designed for graph-structured data. It extends the standard convolutional layer in CNNs, which is typically constrained to grid-based data due to its shareable convolution window. Instead, the MAg layer employs fully trainable, local weighted aggregations based on a message-passing scheme, where each node’s neighborhood is determined by the graph connectivity (adjacency matrix).

By incorporating multiple channels, the MAg layer enhances the network’s ability to capture nonlinearities. In this setup, each node holds a vector of features, effectively creating multiple channels within the same graph structure. The transformation from input to output multi-channel graphs is achieved by performing multiple MAg aggregations across vector data, generating corresponding output components. While the input and output channels of the network usually have predefined meanings, the number of channels in hidden layers is flexible and can be chosen by the network designer.

Formally, the MAg layer is defined as a parameterized transformation between input and output nodes:

$$d_{i,\alpha}^{l+1} = \sigma \left(b_{i,\alpha}^{l+1} + \sum_{\beta=1}^{c_l} \sum_{j \in N_i} k_{i,j,\alpha,\beta}^{l+1} d_{j,\beta}^l \right), \quad (7)$$

where $N_i = \{j \mid A_{ij} = 1\}$ represents the neighborhood of node i , and α and β denote the output and input channels, respectively. The parameters $k_{i,j,\alpha,\beta}^{l+1}$ and $b_{i,\alpha}^{l+1}$ are trainable weights and biases. Unlike traditional convolutional layers, these kernel parameters are not shared, they can be trained independently for each aggregation window, providing greater flexibility in the learning process.

2.2 Graph pooling and unpooling layers

The approach used in this network divides the graph into disjoint cliques (i.e., fully connected subgraphs) and contracts each clique into a single vertex, with new edges representing previously connected cliques. The partitioning is performed statically during the graph U-Net construction and remains independent of the input data.

Given an input graph G , defined by a set of vertices S , and an adjacency matrix A , it is generated a partition of S into N non-overlapping cliques G_1, G_2, \dots, G_N , such that:

$$S = \bigcup_{i=1}^N S_i, \quad \forall i, \forall j, k \in S_i, \quad A_{jk} = 1, \quad \text{and} \quad S_i \cap S_j = \emptyset \text{ for } i \neq j. \quad (8)$$

Each set S_i represents the nodes belonging to the respective subgraph G_i . The resulting pooled graph \tilde{G} consists of vertices:

$$\tilde{S} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}, \quad (9)$$

with edges defined by the pooled adjacency matrix \tilde{A} . The pooling operation is then performed as:

$$d_{i,\beta}^{l+1} = \text{aggr}_{j \in S_i} d_{j,\beta}^l, \quad (10)$$

where the aggregation function (aggr) can be max, min, or average. Importantly, the number of channels remains unchanged, as pooling is applied independently to each input channel.

Graph pooling can be applied multiple times in the encoding stage of the U-Net. To enable future unpooling operations, after each pooling step, we store the original graph G , adjacency matrix A , and the pooling subgraphs G_i . Then, we update the graph as:

$$G \leftarrow \tilde{G}, \quad A \leftarrow \tilde{A}. \quad (11)$$

Graph unpooling is the inverse operation of pooling, restoring the original topology of the input graph from the corresponding pooling layer. This operation is defined using the previously stored subgraphs G_j with nodes S_j :

$$d_{i,\beta}^{l+1} = d_{j,\beta}^l, \quad \forall i \in S_j. \quad (12)$$

Here, the features of node j are replicated to the nodes in S_j , making it analogous to the upsampling operation in CNNs.

Concatenation, also known as skip connections, is a key feature of U-Net architectures. It allows layers in the decoder to access features from the encoder, mitigating vanishing gradient issues and preserving information lost during pooling.

In this framework, concatenation is applied at each unpooling stage by stacking the output of an unpooling layer l with the input of the corresponding pooling layer l' :

$$d_{i,c_l+\alpha}^{l+1} = d_{i,\alpha}^{l'}. \quad (13)$$

Here, c_l represents the number of channels in the unpooling inputs, leading to an output with $c_l + c_{l'}$ channels.

During a forward pass of the MAg layer, aggregation occurs locally at each node, meaning information exchange is limited to directly connected nodes in the adjacency matrix A . Nodes that are not directly connected do not exchange information in a single MAg operation.

To facilitate long-distance information flow, it is used a method to increase the support of the MAg operation by considering higher powers of the adjacency matrix, such as A^2 or A^3 , effectively expanding the receptive field.

The motivation behind using pooling and unpooling layers is to reduce the effective graph size while preserving important feature information. The pooled graph provides a coarsened representation of the original, where each pooled node aggregates information from multiple parent nodes. This hierarchical representation enables long-range information exchange with fewer MAg layers. Furthermore, nested pooling operations result in an exponential reduction of graph diameter, improving efficiency.

3 IMAGE MESH GENERATION

In this chapter, we present a comprehensive pipeline for image mesh generation, a process that converts pixel-based image representations into structured and unstructured mesh formats. We begin by detailing methods for generating both structured grids, using a uniform lattice based on the image domain, and unstructured grids, which involve adaptive sampling along boundaries and within interiors. We then explore techniques such as Delaunay triangulation to ensure well-formed triangular meshes and apply Laplacian smoothing to enhance mesh quality. This framework is adapted from the methodologies described in the literature [2].

An image can be represented as a 2D array of pixels, each corresponding to a point in a Cartesian coordinate system. For a grayscale image, a mesh can be generated based on the object of interest, allowing for structured representation of its shape.

3.1 Structured and Unstructured Grid Generation

To generate a structured grid, the image domain (W, H) is discretized into a uniform lattice of points spaced at intervals of $\Delta x = \Delta y = 10$, given by:

$$x_i = i \times \Delta x, \quad y_j = j \times \Delta y. \quad (14)$$

Filtered points are extracted using the binary mask, retaining only those satisfying:

$$I_{\text{binary}}(x_p, y_p) = 255. \quad (15)$$

For enhanced flexibility, an unstructured grid is introduced, where boundary points are sampled and distributed evenly along the segmented region. Given an ordered boundary set $B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_n\}$, new points along the boundary are placed at:

$$\mathbf{p}_i = b_i + t(b_{i+1} - b_i), \quad (16)$$

where $t = \frac{d - \text{current_length}}{L_i}$ ensures even spacing d . Interior points are sampled via Poisson disk sampling, maintaining minimum distances d_{min} within the region and d_{boundary} from the boundary.

3.2 Delaunay Triangulation and Laplacian Smoothing

Delaunay triangulation ensures well-shaped triangles by enforcing the circumcircle property: for a given set of points P , no point lies inside any triangle's circumcircle. Given three points p_i, p_j, p_k , the condition is satisfied when:

$$|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j| \cdot |\mathbf{p}_j - \mathbf{p}_k| \cdot |\mathbf{p}_k - \mathbf{p}_i|. \quad (17)$$

Once triangulated, the mesh quality is refined using Laplacian smoothing. Each interior point \mathbf{p}_i is updated iteratively based on its neighbors $N(i)$:

$$\mathbf{p}_i^{\text{new}} = \frac{1}{|N(i)|} \sum_{j \in N(i)} \mathbf{p}_j. \quad (18)$$

This ensures a well-conditioned mesh while preserving the boundary structure.

4 MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS OF THE LOSS FUNCTION

The loss function $L(D_{tr}, \theta)$ plays a pivotal role in the supervised learning framework of the Graph U-Net, guiding the model's optimization process. It quantifies the discrepancy between the predicted outputs, $\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta)$, and the true target values, u_m , across the training dataset. By minimizing this loss, the model iteratively refines its parameters, ultimately converging toward an optimal set, θ^* , that enhances predictive accuracy and generalization.

As shown above, the loss function is defined as:

$$L(D_{tr}, \theta) = \frac{1}{M_{tr}} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{tr}} \|\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta) - u_m\|^2, \quad (19)$$

where:

- D_{tr} is the training dataset, consisting of M_{tr} input-output pairs: $\{(f_1, u_1), \dots, (f_{M_{tr}}, u_{M_{tr}})\}$,
- f_m is the m -th input feature (in this case, mesh-based data),
- u_m is the corresponding m -th target output,
- $\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta)$ represents the output of the MAgNET (Graph U-Net) given input f_m and parameters θ ,
- θ is the set of all trainable parameters in the network,
- $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the L_2 norm (Euclidean distance),
- The summation is over all M_{tr} training examples,
- The loss is the mean squared error between the network's predictions $\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta)$ and the true outputs u_m .

The goal of training is to find the optimal parameters θ^* that minimize this loss function:

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} L(D_{tr}, \theta) \quad (20)$$

This formulation demonstrates that MAgNET employs a standard mean squared error loss function, commonly used in regression tasks such as predicting displacement fields in mesh-based simulations. The U-Net architecture is integrated through the function \mathcal{G} , representing the forward pass through the entire MAgNET Graph U-Net. The loss function computes the mean squared error over all M_{tr} training samples, ensuring the model minimizes the average squared difference between predictions and true values for accurate generalization.

To gain deeper insights into the optimization process, we examine the loss function's behavior by analyzing its convexity and smoothness properties. Understanding these characteristics is crucial for assessing convergence, stability, and overall performance of the optimization algorithm.

4.1 Convexity and Smoothness Analysis

The loss function defined by (19) is inherently non-convex due to the nonlinearity introduced by the activation functions, pooling operations, and learnable parameters in the Graph U-Net. However, in local neighborhoods where gradients are well-behaved, the function may exhibit local convexity [6].

To formally analyze convexity, we examine the Hessian matrix for (19). The Hessian is given by:

$$H = \nabla_{\theta}^2 L(D_{tr}, \theta). \quad (21)$$

To determine local convexity, we examine the Hessian matrix $\nabla_{\theta}^2 L$. We will abbreviate $L(D_{tr}, \theta)$ as $L(\theta)$. If the Hessian is positive semi-definite ($\nabla_{\theta}^2 L \succeq 0$) in a neighborhood, the loss is locally convex there. However, due to the high dimensionality of θ , computing the full Hessian is computationally expensive. Instead, we approximate local convexity using second-order Taylor expansions:

$$L(\theta + \Delta\theta) \approx L(\theta) + \nabla_{\theta} L \cdot \Delta\theta + \frac{1}{2} \Delta\theta^T \nabla_{\theta}^2 L \Delta\theta. \quad (22)$$

Local convexity holds if the quadratic term $\frac{1}{2} \Delta\theta^T \nabla_{\theta}^2 L \Delta\theta \geq 0$ for all $\Delta\theta$. [7]

In neural networks, the Hessian can have both positive and negative eigenvalues, indicating the presence of saddle points and local minima, which confirms the general non-convex nature of the loss landscape. However, certain architectures and regularization techniques, such as weight decay, can promote local convexity in regions of interest.

Theorem 1. *Suppose that the function $\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta)$ (19) is twice continuously differentiable with respect to θ . Then, the Hessian matrix $\nabla_{\theta}^2 L$ is locally positive semi-definite.*

Proof. The loss function (19) is a sum of squared differences, which can be rewritten as:

$$L(\theta) = \frac{1}{M_{tr}} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{tr}} (\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta) - u_m)^T (\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta) - u_m). \quad (23)$$

To compute the Hessian, we begin by calculating the gradient with respect to the variable θ :

$$\nabla_{\theta} L = \frac{2}{M_{tr}} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{tr}} J_m^T (\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta) - u_m), \quad (24)$$

where $J_m = \frac{\partial \mathcal{G}}{\partial \theta}(f_m, \theta)$ is the Jacobian matrix.

Now, differentiating again,

$$\nabla_{\theta}^2 L = \frac{2}{M_{tr}} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{tr}} \left(J_m^T J_m + \sum_i (\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta) - u_m)_i \frac{\partial^2 (\mathcal{G})_i}{\partial \theta^2}(f_m, \theta) \right). \quad (25)$$

The first term of (25), $J_m^T J_m$, is a Gram matrix [8], which is positive semi-definite because for any vector v , we have:

$$v^T J_m^T J_m v = \|J_m v\|^2 \geq 0. \quad (26)$$

The second term of (25) involves second derivatives but is a weighted sum of Hessians of \mathcal{G} . If \mathcal{G} is linear or approximately linear in θ , this term vanishes, leaving only $J_m^T J_m$, which is positive semi-definite. Even when this term does not vanish, it does not necessarily introduce negative eigenvalues.

In regions where the second term is small (e.g., near minima where the Hessian is dominated by the first term and is therefore positive semi-definite).

$$(\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta) - u_m)_i \approx 0 \quad (27)$$

Thus, $\nabla_{\theta}^2 L$ is locally positive semi-definite, proving the theorem. \square

Theorem 2. *The loss function (19) is L_s -smooth if its gradient is Lipschitz continuous, i.e., there exists a constant $L_s > 0$ such that*

$$\|\nabla L(\theta_1) - \nabla L(\theta_2)\| \leq L_s \|\theta_1 - \theta_2\|, \quad \forall \theta_1, \theta_2. \quad (28)$$

The presence of activation functions such as ReLU introduces piecewise linearity, potentially causing non-smooth regions where the gradient is discontinuous. In contrast, sigmoid and tanh activations ensure smoothness but can lead to vanishing gradient issues, affecting optimization dynamics.

Proof. The smoothness of $L(\theta)$ depends on the properties of the function $\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta)$. We analyze the gradient behavior to establish Lipschitz continuity.

As in (24), the gradient of $L(\theta)$ is given by:

$$\nabla_{\theta} L = \frac{2}{M_{tr}} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{tr}} J_m(f_m, \theta)^T (\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta) - u_m), \quad (29)$$

where $J_m(f_m, \theta)$ is the Jacobian of \mathcal{G} with respect to θ .

To establish the Lipschitz condition, we analyze the difference:

$$\|\nabla L(\theta_1) - \nabla L(\theta_2)\| = \left\| \frac{2}{M_{tr}} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{tr}} J_m(f_m, \tilde{\theta})^T (\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta_1) - \mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta_2)) \right\|, \quad (30)$$

where $\tilde{\theta}$ is an intermediate point between θ_1 and θ_2 .

Using the submultiplicative property of norms,

$$\|\nabla L(\theta_1) - \nabla L(\theta_2)\| \leq \frac{2}{M_{tr}} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{tr}} \|J_m(f_m, \tilde{\theta})^T\| \cdot \|\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta_1) - \mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta_2)\|. \quad (31)$$

If \mathcal{G} is Lipschitz with constant $L_{\mathcal{G}}$, i.e.,

$$\|\mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta_1) - \mathcal{G}(f_m, \theta_2)\| \leq L_{\mathcal{G}} \|\theta_1 - \theta_2\|, \quad (32)$$

and the Jacobian is bounded such that $\|J_m(f_m, \tilde{\theta})^T\| \leq J_{\max}$, then

$$\|\nabla L(\theta_1) - \nabla L(\theta_2)\| \leq \frac{2J_{\max}L_{\mathcal{G}}}{M_{tr}} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{tr}} \|\theta_1 - \theta_2\|. \quad (33)$$

Thus, setting $L_s = 2J_{\max}L_{\mathcal{G}}$, we obtain the desired Lipschitz condition.

The impact of activation functions on smoothness is significant:

- **ReLU:** Since it is piecewise linear, it can introduce non-smooth points where the gradient is discontinuous [9].
- **Sigmoid and Tanh:** These functions ensure smoothness but suffer from vanishing gradients, making optimization difficult [10].

Thus, the choice of activation functions plays a crucial role in maintaining smoothness while ensuring effective gradient-based optimization. □

Overall, the interplay between convexity and smoothness in the loss function significantly influences optimization efficiency. These properties aids in selecting suitable training strategies, such as adaptive gradient methods, second-order optimization techniques, and appropriate regularization schemes to enhance convergence stability.

5 RESULTS

In this chapter, we present the experimental results that evaluate the performance of our proposed approach. For this purpose, we utilize two images with irregular forms. The process begins with image processing and mesh generation, followed by finite element method (FEM) simulations to create reference data, and concludes with the MAgNET simulation.

Our process starts by reading an input image, which is then converted to a binary image using Otsu’s thresholding. Contours are detected from the binary image, and the contour representing the object of interest is selected. This contour defines the object’s boundary, which is used for mesh generation. The mesh is generated using the method described in Chapter 3.

Figure 1a shows the generated mesh overlaid on the original image for Image 1, with the boundary points highlighted and the triangulation clearly visible. Similarly, Figure 1b illustrates the mesh for Image 2.

To create these meshes, we used the parameters presented in Table 1.

(a) Mesh overlay on the first image, showing the extracted boundary and Delaunay triangulation.

(b) Mesh overlay on the second image, displaying the refined mesh with Delaunay triangulation.

Figure 1: Meshes generated for two different images after applying Delaunay triangulation.

A FEniCS mesh is then constructed from the transformed points and the validated triangles. This mesh serves as the computational domain for our elasticity simulation. The mesh will be transferred to the neural network using the corresponding adjacency matrix. For the FEM simulation, we define a two-dimensional elasticity problem using a linear elastic material model. The material properties are characterized by Young’s modulus and Poisson’s ratio. Boundary conditions are applied on the left boundary to fix the displacement, and a subset of nodes is designated as fixed to simulate additional constraints. Random force values are applied to specific nodes (representing force application points) to generate a variety of simulation scenarios. For each simulation, the weak form of the elasticity problem is assembled and solved using a direct solver, yielding the displacement field across the mesh.

To create the dataset, multiple simulation samples are generated. For each sample, the resulting displacement field is extracted and stored, while the applied force vectors are recorded as features. The displacement results are concatenated into a single vector for each sample, and the entire dataset is split into training and testing subsets. These data arrays are then saved to CSV files for subsequent deep learning tasks.

Table 1 lists the key parameters used throughout the process for two images.

With the FEM-generated dataset and corresponding mesh connectivity now available, we proceed to implement the MAgNET deep learning framework.

The MAgNET simulation begins with data preprocessing, where the FEM-generated displacement and force data are formatted for input into the network. The model is then

Table 1: Key parameters used for Image-to-Mesh Conversion, FEM Simulation, and Dataset Creation for two images.

Parameter	Image 1	Image 2	Description
Number of Boundary Points	20	35	Points uniformly sampled along the contour.
Number of Interior Points	15	25	Interior points are uniformly sampled from within the contour.
Minimum Distance (Interior)	10	10	Minimum separation between interior points.
Minimum Distance to Boundary	15	10	Minimum separation of interior points from the boundary.
Young's Modulus, E	500	600	Elastic modulus used in the FEM simulation.
Poisson's Ratio, ν	0.3	0.3	Material Poisson's ratio used to derive the Lamé parameters.
Number of FEM Samples	5000	5000	Total number of simulation samples generated for the dataset.
Force Range	8 to 12	8 to 12	Range of force values applied at designated force nodes, in Newton.

trained on the training subset of the dataset, optimizing its parameters to minimize the error between the predicted displacements and the FEM reference values.

After training, we evaluate the performance of MAgNET on the testing subset. Figure 2 shows a comparison between the displacement fields predicted by MAgNET for Image 1 and those obtained from FEM simulations for a representative sample. Similarly, Figure 3 presents the corresponding comparison for Image 2.

The results demonstrate that MAgNET accurately reproduces the displacement patterns, offering a substantial improvement in computational efficiency over conventional FEM methods.

These findings suggest that MAgNET is a promising alternative for rapid, image-based assessment of material behavior, with significant potential for real-time monitoring and design optimization in engineering applications.

Figure 2: Comparison of displacement fields for Image 1: FEM simulation versus MAgNET predictions.

Figure 3: Comparison of displacement fields for Image 2: FEM simulation versus MAgNET predictions.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we developed a comprehensive workflow that integrates image processing, mesh generation, FEM simulations, and a deep learning framework (MAgNET) to predict displacement fields directly from image data. Our experimental results demonstrate that the MAgNET framework is capable of closely reproducing the displacement fields obtained via traditional FEM simulations, while significantly reducing computational overhead.

This approach has the potential to enable rapid, image-based assessments of material behavior, which is particularly beneficial for real-time monitoring and design optimization in engineering applications.

Despite the promising results, certain limitations were identified, such as challenges in mesh quality for highly irregular shapes and the dependency on specific simulation parameters. Future research could address these limitations by refining the mesh generation process, exploring alternative deep learning architectures, and extending the methodology to a wider variety of materials and loading conditions.

Overall, this study contributes a novel method for coupling traditional simulation techniques with advanced neural network models, paving the way for more efficient and accessible simulation tools in engineering practice.

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